

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF CAREER ORIENTATION OF
ADOLESCENT STUDENTS.

Baqoyeva Zarina Rayimovna. zbakaeva69@gmail.com

Teacher of the Department of General Psychology, TDPU named after Nizomi

Mahmudjonov Behruzbek

*Student of Information Systems and Technologies, Faculty of Professional Education,
Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomiy*

Abstract: Choosing a profession requires two types of information from an early adolescent: awareness of the professional world and requirements for each profession; to know their abilities and interests. Both that information and this information are not enough for early teenagers. The implementation of life plans and the choice of a profession of early adolescents depend on social conditions, especially the level of general education of parents. The choice of a profession for early adolescents is primarily a moral problem. In the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with the right to work, a person has the right to choose a profession according to his ability, talent and interest.

Key words: profession, psychologist, professional training, personality development, interest, intellect, professional choice.

We know that the development, social, political and economic stability of any society depends on the highly developed intellectual and moral potential of its citizens. After all, the national issue of personnel training plays an important role in the spiritual renewal of our society, in the formation of a socially oriented market economy, and in the formation of a socially oriented market economy. Because, on the basis of the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, the formation of a new system of training of highly trained personnel based on the new achievements of modern culture, economy, science and technology, has become one of the important conditions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a human child matures, he strives for knowledge and enlightenment. He takes his first lesson at school. But it is natural that some problems related to the education of young people, who are the owners of our future, make people think today.

How do teenage students, who are just growing up, approach the profession? Many people are interested in this problem. It is known from observations and life experience that usually boys and girls in early adolescence have difficulty expressing a clear, reasonable opinion about taking an independent step in life. Therefore, during the period of choosing a profession, they do not know how to behave rationally and correctly, they are confused or take risks. As a result, unpleasant experiences, disappointments, and social laziness occur. Some of the students of the upper class imitate obvious examples in choosing a profession, and they do not have ideas directed towards a certain goal. It is the same effect of the behavior and actions of the environment that leads to the origin of hesitations and disappointments in relation to the chosen profession during the period when they choose a profession and carry out educational activities in this regard. Therefore, when choosing a profession, pedagogues and parents are required to direct young people to the profession based on their abilities and capabilities, that is, based on their individual characteristics. In today's era of science, technology and social development, ensuring the participation of young people in building society is the most important task of today's school. As it is known, in orientation to a profession, it is necessary to choose taking into account the individual characteristics and interests of each person, as well as the need to ensure the needs of society in relation to a certain profession. The correct orientation to the profession allows a person to find the right path in his life. In order to

prepare students for independent work and achieve their choice of profession according to their abilities, it is necessary for school teachers to have high pedagogical skills, knowledge level, perceptive, academic, communicative skills related to professions. development of the activities of science circles, organization of lectures on the profession in schools will give results, as well as seminars - training sessions, conversations and discussions in schools on topics such as "My profession's pride", "My profession's future program" organization of meetings, exhibitions related to professions, arouses students' interest and enthusiasm in choosing a profession. Vocational orientation of students in general education schools is carried out together with school management, school psychologists, vocational guidance specialists and teachers.

Each personality type is an idealistic type oriented to a certain professional environment - technological process and technical devices for the creation of material goods, talent - mental work, interaction with social - economic work, conventional clearly structured activities, business - leadership of people and artistic - to creativity. each personality type model is built according to the following scheme: goals, values, interests, abilities, desired professional roles, possible achievements, career, etc. It is based on taking into account the organization skills of the following professions. There have been several attempts to systematize occupations based on required skills. Originally proposed by D Paterson in 1953. Let's focus on systematization of professions. It is very common and is based on 9 different skills. Using the Minnesota Occupational Rating Scale (MORS), 432 occupations are selected by occupational psychologists and divided into the following 7 groups. Academic, mechanical, social, religious, musical, artistic and physical groups. As a result of summarizing the results of the graduate work, 432 professions were brought to 214 samples, of which 137 are one profession and 77 combine two to 18 specialties. According to working conditions, YE.A. Klimov divides professions into 4 groups. Work close to household microclimate. (B) professions related to being outdoors in different weather conditions, agronomist, welder, traffic inspector. Working at height, under water, at high and low levels under unusual conditions: a diver, a firefighter, etc. Work in conditions of high responsibility for people's health and life: material values, kindergarten educator, teacher, investigator. Using conventional symbols, it is possible to create a "map" of the world of professions and a sample formula of a certain profession. This formula can be applied to both the real profession and the dream profession. 1. My profession 2. Groups of professions 3. Departments of professions 4. Classes of professions 5. Classification of types of professions This is intended for career guidance. V. E. Govrilov, who studied this classification, pointed out its disadvantages as well as its positive aspects. For example, professions in one group contain components that impose opposite demands on the worker, which makes it difficult to determine the signs of professional competence. Another disadvantage of the classification is that the world of professions is extremely variable, and accordingly, the content of work of professions is also variable. This creates uncertainty regarding the structuring of professions and makes it difficult to enter the professional selection process into the vocational counseling process. It is known that vocational training cannot be carried out in all professions, and the degree of complexity, conditions, means, and content of the types of professional activities are very different. Since teenagers do not have clear ideas about professions, they are prone to mistakes. they put They do not understand what personal qualities are required for the chosen and necessary profession. However, there are opportunities to prevent and eliminate such disappointments, and these factors can be cited as follows: - development of methods of

learning professions, their classification and expression; - psychologists carry out propaganda work on professions, give advice to students on professions; - review of career guidance activities together with a psychologist and parents; - introducing teenagers to the main types of profession; - preparing high school students for the profession and awakening their interest in labor education classes; - development of applied psychodiagnostic methods of career selection; - such as psychological training and propaganda work among teenagers regarding career guidance.

CONCLUSION Professional activity is important in everyone's life. Parents think about their children's future from the first steps. By observing their children's interests and abilities, they try to determine their professional future. Many school graduates wonder who I will be in the future or what field I will be a specialist in? - they put the question in front of themselves and face the problem of choosing a profession. As a result, the majors are randomly chosen by the students. Some of the school graduates immediately get a job without any special training or understanding of their professional future. There are many such examples.

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